

Correlation of Glycemic Control in Newborn at Birth in Relation to Maternal Glycemic Control in Diabetic Mothers

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Received: 05-11-2024 / Revised: 13-11-2024 / Accepted: 23-12-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Maternal HbA1c levels have been found to correlate closely with the occurrence of congenital malformations and other neonatal complications characteristic of pregnant diabetic women. This study was conducted to investigate the correlation of glycemic control in newborn at birth in relation to maternal glycemic control in diabetic mothers.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was carried out at a Tertiary care hospital of south east India for a period of one year. Study included 84 babies born to mothers with Gestational diabetes or Type I or Type II DM. Maternal HbA1c was done before delivery by HPLC, and all babies were subjected to random blood sugar as per protocol for infant of diabetic mother (IDM) i.e. at 0, 1, 2, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48 hours of life by glucometer. Glycosylated Haemoglobin of the newborn was done at 24hrs after birth by HPLC, and 2D ECHO was performed on each baby to see for any structural or functional abnormality of the heart.

Results: There was no statistically significant difference between mean birth weight and gender ($p > 0.05$) in IDM. 71.4% of patients were AGA. There was no significant difference between mean HbA1c of neonate ($5.87\% \pm 0.61$) and mean maternal HbA1c ($5.69\% \pm 0.73$) ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: This study concluded that IDM babies are at risk of hypoglycemia if the mother's HbA1c level go beyond 6.5%.

Keywords: Birth weight, Congenital abnormalities, Newborn

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a fairly common medical complication of pregnancy associated with maternal, fetal & neonatal morbidities and mortalities. The incidence of diabetes in pregnancy is approximately 1 in 1000 of the overall number of pregnancies for a given population. [1] Perinatal outcome & long term neurologic sequels in infants of diabetic mothers is related to the onset and duration of glucose intolerance and to the severity of the disease in the mother. Maternal HbA1C levels have been found to correlate closely with the occurrence of congenital malformations & other neonatal complications characteristic of pregnant diabetic women. [2] Among the various metabolic consequences these infants of diabetic mother (IDM) suffer, hypoglycaemia is the commonest and most serious because of its association with both acute decompensation and long-term neuronal loss. Most IDMs are prone to develop severe but

asymptomatic hypoglycaemia during the first post-natal hours. [2] Poor glycemic control in the diabetic mother results in foetal hyperglycaemia which ultimately results in hyperplasia of the islets of Langerhans, increased peripheral insulin receptors, a decreased glucagon response to hypoglycaemia and a delayed evocation of hepatic gluconeogenic pathway. [3] Poor maternal glycemic control during the third trimester has been shown to be strongly and independently correlated with neonatal hypoglycaemia requiring intervention. [4] Consumption of glucose by the brain cells is high, and thus, neurons and glial cells are susceptible to hypoglycaemia. [3] Neonatal seizures, coma, brain damage results from unrecognized postnatal hypoglycaemia. Fortunately, in most of these neonates, hypoglycaemia is transient and asymptomatic. However, if the diagnosis is missed, and the neonate fails to achieve normo-glycaemia, it may become symptomatic and suffer long

term complications of cerebral injury. It would be useful, therefore, if we could predict foetal hypoglycaemia from the state of maternal glycaemic control. [5] This study was conducted to investigate the correlation of glycaemic control in newborn at birth in relation to maternal glycaemic control in diabetic mothers.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was carried out at a Tertiary care hospital of south east India from March 2018 to April 2019, after obtaining approval from Institutional Ethical Committee. All babies born to mothers with Gestational diabetes or Type I or Type II DM were enrolled in the study, while mothers with HbA1c not tested and those not giving consent were excluded from the study. Written informed consent was obtained from each mother prior to their enrolment in the study. Brief case history including type and definition of DM of mother was recorded in pre-designed proformas. Detailed anthropometry of the baby was taken and baby were classified as AGA (Babies with birth weight between 10th to 90th percentiles for the period of their gestation are called appropriate for gestational age[6]); SGA (Babies with birth weight less than 10th percentile or 2SD for the period of their gestation are called small for gestational age[7]), LGA (Babies with birth weight more than 90th percentile or 2SD for the period of

their gestation age are called large for gestational age[6,7]) as per Lubchenco’s chart. Maternal HbA1c was done before delivery by HPLC, and all babies were subjected to random blood sugar as per protocol for IDM i.e. at 0, 1, 2, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48 hours of life by glucometer. Glycosylated Haemoglobin of the newborn was done at 24hrs after birth by HPLC, and 2D ECHO was performed on each baby to see for any structural or functional abnormality of the heart. Criteria for diagnosis of impaired glucose tolerance and DM with 75g oral glucose was as follows: Good glycaemic control: HbA1c level <6.5%; Normal range of HbA1c: 4-5.6%; Increased risk of DM: HbA1c level 5.7-6.4%; DM: HbA1c level ≥6.5%.

Statistical Analysis: The data was analysed using EPI Info 7.1. Repeated measures Analysis of variance has been applied to find the difference means in more than two groups. Pearson’s correlation coefficients were used to depict the strength of correlation between two continuous variables. p value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

There was no statistically significant difference between mean birth weight and gender (p>0.05) in IDM. (Table 1)

Table 1: Showing distribution of mean birth weight and gender in IDM in our setting

Gender	N	Mean Birth Weight	Std. Error Mean	T value	P value
Male	56(66.2%)	2.818±0.513	0.0691	0.842	0.404
Female	28(33.7%)	2.629±0.633	0.1218		
Total	84(100%)	2.755±0.563	0.0617		

There was no significant correlation between duration of Diabetes detected during ANC and Neonatal HbA1c (%) (Table 2)

Table 2: Distribution of study subjects based on Gestation at which Diabetes was diagnosed in mother

Trimester	Patients Detected with Diabetes (n=84)	Mean Neonatal HbA1c (%)	P Value
First	7(8.3%)	5.93	0.987
Second	57(67.8%)	5.8	
Third	20 (23.81%)	6.06	

71% of patients were AGA. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Pie diagram showing distribution of AGA, LGA, SGA babies

There was no significant difference between mean HbA1c of neonate ($5.87\% \pm 0.61$) and mean maternal HbA1c ($5.69\% \pm 0.73$) ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that maternal glycaemic control is well transmitted to newborns. Repeated measure ANOVA showed blood sugar in neonates was not different at various timings from birth to 48 hrs ($p > 0.05$). (Table 3)

Table 3: Mean Neonatal Blood Glucose levels in mg/dl at different timings after birth.

Descriptive Statistics		
	Mean	Std. Deviation
blood sugar in mg/dl at 0 hr	78.93	15.81
blood sugar in mg/dl at 1 hr	76.6	12.61
blood sugar in mg/dl at 2 hr	77.94	12.54
blood sugar in mg/dl at 3 hr	77.27	10.94
blood sugar in mg/dl at 6 hr	77.85	12.58
blood sugar in mg/dl at 12 hr	78.17	11.37
blood sugar in mg/dl at 24 hr	75.52	9.53
blood sugar in mg/dl at 48 hr	77.07	9.76

There was no correlation of blood sugar level till 48 hr with maternal HbA1c of 6.5%, but there was a significant co-relation of maternal HbA1c level above 6.5. (Table 4)

Table 4: Correlation of Maternal HbA1c with Neonatal blood sugar levels

Neonatal Blood sugar in mg/dl at 48 hr					
Maternal- HbA1c%	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value	Correlation
<5.5	30	78.77	10.63	0.022	0.284
5.5-6	24	76.92	9.45		-0.129
6-6.5	19	79.26	9.06		-0.042
>6.5	11	69	4.56		-0.353
Total	84	77.07	9.76		-0.155

The mean neonatal blood sugar level was significantly higher in patient with mean neonatal HbA1c level above 6.5% ($p = 0.008$). (Table 5)

Table 5: Correlation of Neonatal HbA1c with Neonatal mean blood sugar levels at 48 hrs.

Neonatal mean Blood Sugar in mg/dl @ 48 hrs					
Neonate-HbA1c (%)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value	Correlation
<5.5	17	78.06	9.21	0.0082	-0.128
5.5-6	28	76.32	9.39		0.169
6-6.5	28	74.43	10.27		0.079
>6.5	11	84.18	7.35		0.049
Total	84	77.07	9.76		0.092

Discussion

Several studies have stated that good glycaemic control during pregnancy in overweight, non-diabetic women play a major part to prevent neonatal complication. Fetal hyperglycemia is crucial in development of postnatal hypoglycemia as well as macrosomia and other congenital malformations. This study aimed investigate the correlation of glycaemic control in newborn at birth in relation to maternal glycaemic control in diabetic mothers. In this study, mean birth weight of neonates was 2.75 ± 0.56 , with majority being male (66.2%). Similar observations were made in the study by Haider S et al [8], wherein, 58% of newborns were male.

High maternal HbA1c in third trimester could be associated with foetal macrosomia as it was found in this study as well as the study by Sailo L et al [1].

However, no significant correlation was found in this study, which may be because of other factor affecting foetal growth like maternal nutrition, genetic constitution and various maternal disease. The reports on relationship between birth weight and glycosylated haemoglobin have been conflicting and there are also reports with diabetic mother having normal HbA1c with CGA babies. In this study, 5.91% of babies were LGA, and the maternal HbA1c levels were deranged in all these babies. In a similar study by Meenakshi G et al [9], macrosomia was not found in any of the babies, which they attributed to tight control of GDM. Haider S et al [8] documented hypoglycaemia in 28% and association of asymmetrical septal hypertrophy along with macrosomia in 16% of babies, which is higher than our study (5.91%). This higher incidence of macrosomia in their study was attributed to high HbA1c levels of

>8.5% which was seen in 58% of mothers in their study.

HbA1c is a valid index of glycaemia. [10] In our study, all mothers who had HbA1c of <7%, which signifies good control, was reflected in baby of known morbidity and mortality. Aggressive control of maternal glycaemic status is warranted because most morbidities are epidemiologically and pathophysiologically closely linked to foetal hyperglycaemia and hyperinsulinaemia. [11] In this study, most of our mothers had controlled GDM and hence we did not find much cases of hypoglycaemia, congenital anomalies and significant macrosomia which are the main morbidities related to uncontrolled GDM. We have observed two cases of congenital heart diseases in our study as evident on echocardiography. Haider S et al [8] observed congenital anomalies of which cardiac anomalies predominated with 94% in their study, which was attributed to uncontrolled diabetes. Gonzalez-Quintero VH [12] found higher incidence of macrosomic hypoglycemia, jaundice and still birth in the suboptimally controlled GDM as compared to controlled GDM.

One study suggested that glucose monitoring in IDM need to be done only during initial 2 hrs of life, [13] while we have observed the blood sugar level till 48 hours in our study. We observed significant association of neonatal hypoglycemia with cord HbA1c level of >6.5%, which is similar to previous study. [14] Previous literature has stated that even asymptomatic hypoglycemia may be a risk factor for impaired neurodevelopment and must therefore be identified, prevented and treated. [15] We observed transmission of mother's glycemic control to newborn which act as a screening test and thereby helps preventing asymptomatic hypoglycaemia and long-term neurologic dysfunction which can be as mild as learning disabilities to as major as seizures disorder in future life.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Neonatal HbA1c correlates well with maternal HbA1c level after birth. IDM babies are at risk of hypoglycemia if the mother's HbA1c level go beyond 6.5%. There was no significant co-relation found between neonatal HbA1c levels and neonatal blood sugar till 48 hours in babies with maternal HbA1c level <6.5. There was no significant correlation between duration of diabetes and hypoglycemia and other congenital anomalies associated with gestational diabetes.

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